

SPORTCHI YOSHLARNING MA’NAVYI-AXLOQIY TARBIYASINI SHAKLLANTIRISH

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“Ijtimoiy va tabiiy fanlar” kafedrasini o’qituvchisi.

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Annotatsiya. Mazkur maqolada yosh sportchilar o’rtasida ma’naviy-axloqiy tarbiyasini shakllantirish jarayonida jismoniy tarbiya va sportning o’rni masalasi keltirilgan, shuningdek, ushbu masalaning dolzarbligi, uning zarurati, yoshlarning ma’naviy-axloqiy tarbiyasini tarbiyalashda jismoniy tarbiya va sportning ahamiyati haqida so’z borgan.

Kalit so’zlar: gimnastika, musoboqa, yosh sportchilar, sifatlar.

Mustaqillikning qo’lga kiritilishi yosh avlodni ma’naviy jihatdan tarbiyalashga bo’lgan ehtiyojni kuchaytirdi. Yoshlar ongida yuksak ma’naviy qadriyatlarni shakllantirish, bir tomondan, ularning kamol topishiga xizmat qilsa, ikkinchi tomondan, mamlakatdagi ma’naviy-ruhiy iqlimni sog’lomlashtirish va aholining jipsligini ta’minlashga ko’maklashadi.

Mamlakatda o’tkazilayotgan chuqur ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy va siyosiy islohotlar bu jarayonda ishtirok etayotgan barcha fuqarolarda muayyan ma’naviy-axloqiy me’yorlar shakllanishini taqozo etadi. Ana shu me’yorlarni yoshlarda shakllantirish ularni hayotga tayyorlashda muhim rol o’ynaydi. Ayniqsa, sportchi yoshlarda yuksak ma’naviy-axloqiy me’yorlarni shakllantirish ularning barkamol bo’lib yetishishida ham katta ahamiyatga ega.

Ma’naviy-axloqiy sifatlar o’z-o’zidan irodaviy sifatlarini ham taqozo etadi. Shuning uchun ham, yosh sportchilarni tarbiyalashda or, g’urur, nomus, uyat kabi insonning ichki kechinmalari va irodaviy sifatlarini aks ettiruvchi hislatlarni shakllantirish ham muhim ahamiyatga ega.

Ma’naviy tarbiyani shakllantirishning asosiy omili sportchilarga belgilangan me’yorlarni tushuntirish, nima axloqiy va nima axloqsizlik ekanligini tushuntirishda emas, balki axloqiy odob qoidalariga rioya etish kerakligi to’g’risidagi e’tiqodning mavjud ekanligidir. Gimnastika musoboqalari jarayonida iroda sifatlarini rivojlantirish darajasi katta ahamiyat kasb etadi. Bir xil taktik faoliyat yo’nalishida jismoniy va texnik jihatdan keng tayyorgarlik ko’rgan sportchilar ichida kimning ma’naviy-irodaviy tayyorgarligi yuqori bo’lsa, odatda o’sha g’olib chiqadi, ya’ni musoboqada kimning to’g’ri qarorlar qabul qilish va ularni muvaffaqiyat bilan amalga oshirish salohiyati yuqori bo’lsa, o’sha sportchi yutadi. Ko’pincha sportchi shunday vaziyatga tushib qoladiki, bunday vaqtlarda undan muayyan bir oqilona yo’lni tanlab olish talab qilinadi. Tabiiyki, bunday qarorlarni qabul qilish uchun sportchiga ma’naviy fazilatlar zarur bo’ladi. Ayniqsa, qarorlar musoboqa jarayonida qabul qilinadigan bo’lsa, sportchidan yanada ko’proq iroda kuchi talab qilinadi. Sportdagi muvaffaqiyatlar ko’p jihatdan sportchining qay darajada biror emotsional kuchga ega ekanligiga, uning o’z holatini boshqara olish mahoratiga, butun kuch-g’ayratini bo’lajak bellashuvga qaratib g’alaba qozonishga sabab bo’ladigan barcha omillar ta’sirini o’zida jamlay olishiga bog’liq bo’ladi.

Murabbiy jamoaning har bir a’zosini bilishi kerak, bu jamoaning psixologik tayyorgarligi uchun juda muhimdir. Shuning uchun sportchi mashaqqatlarni yengib o’tib, qo’yilgan maqsadga erishadigan musoboqalar irodaviy hislatlar uchun oliy sinov vazifasini o’taydi. Qolgan o’zaro teng sharoitlarda kuchli irodaga ega bo’lgan sportchi g’alabaga erishadi. Musoboqada barcha jismoniy-ma’naviy kuchlarni yaqqol namoyon bo’lishini talab etadi. Shuni yodda tutish kerakki, har bir

sport turi o‘ziga xos qiyinchilikka ega bo‘lib, u “o‘lik nuqta” deb ataladi. Sportchi o‘lik nuqtaning yuzaga kelishi mumkinligi haqida hamda uni bartaraf etish yo‘llarini bilishi kerak. Qiyinchiliklar musoboqani o‘tkazilish sharoitlari tufayli kelib chiqishi mumkin.

Yetuk sportchilarni musoboqalarda ishtirok etish amaliyoti ba‘zi sharoitlarni sanab o‘tish imkonini beradi:

1. Onglilik
2. Intizomlilik
3. Qobiliyat va ko‘nikmalar hajmi, saviyasi
4. Sportchini jamoada tutgan o‘rni.

Irodaviy xislatlarning namoyon bo‘lishi uchun muhim usullardan biri – ixlos qilishdir. Sportchi qo‘yilgan maqsadga erishish uchun o‘z irodasiga tasir etishi mumkin. Musoboqa – ma‘naviy-irodaviy xislatlarni tekshirishning asosiy usulidir.

Xulosa qilib aytganda sportchilarning sport musoboqalarida g‘olib chiqishida ma‘naviy-irodaviy tayyorgarligi yuqori darajada bo‘lishi kata ahamiyatga ega, ya‘ni musoboqada to‘g‘ri qarorlarni tezroq qabul qilish va ularni muvaffaqiyat bilan amalga oshirish salohiyati yuqori bo‘lsa, o‘sha sportchi g‘alaba qozonadi.

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